

Laboratory for Food Safety, Maisons-Alfort location

Report

Temperature distribution of ready-to-eat food at retail level in Europe

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Hélène BERGIS, Véronique NOEL, Annie BEAUFORT

Team MOD-AQR, Laboratory for Food Safety, Maisons-Alfort location,
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1 INTRODUCTION

Between January 2010 and January 2012 a European Union baseline survey on the prevalence and level of contamination of *Listeria monocytogenes* in three categories of Ready-To-Eat (RTE) food at retail level was carried out by European countries (mainly EU Member States) under the coordination and funded by Directorate Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE, ex DG SANCO) of European Commission. The protocol had been developed by European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), which also prepared two scientific reports on the results of this survey (EFSA, 2013, 2014).

RTE fishery products, RTE cheese products and RTE heat-treated meat products, were the three categories of RTE food considered in this survey, knowing that these products (2011 EFSA-ECDC annual report) have the highest proportion of non-compliance with *Listeria monocytogenes* criteria.

Beside the estimation of *Listeria monocytogenes* prevalence and its level of contamination in these three types of RTE food, temperatures at the surface of packaged RTE food samples were measured and collected from retail outlets in 26 Member States except Portugal, and in one Non-Member state, Norway.

The retail outlets covered in this survey were supermarkets, shops and other similar outlets that sell directly to the final consumer.

The purpose of this study was to consider the collected RTE food temperatures at retail level in order (i) to get a better knowledge of temperature distribution of RTE food at this specific stage of the cold chain all over Europe, (ii) to better assess shelf-life of RTE food regarding *Listeria monocytogenes*.

2 METHODS

2.1 SAMPLING DESIGN

2.1.1 SAMPLING PLAN

A proportionate stratified sampling plan was used whereby the samples were allocated to every Member State (MS) proportionally to the size of the human population in the MS.

Each MS followed a sampling plan including the major cities/towns to be sampled, the types of retail outlets covered, the percentage of samples to be collected from each category and the timing of sampling through the year.

For the geographical distribution of sampling (% of human population covered) and the selection of the cities / towns to be sampled, the rules were the following:

The sampling took place in at least two large cities/towns in each MS. The cities/towns in which sampling was performed covered at least 30 % of the human population in the MS. However, if the eight largest cities/towns were included in the plan, the human population coverage may be less than 30 %.

For the selection of the timing of sampling, the rules were the following:

To take into account a possible variation in the contamination level of *Listeria monocytogenes* in RTE food over the year, and to ensure accurate results, the duration of the survey was divided in 12 periods of 1 month during which equal numbers of samples were taken.

2.1.2 SELECTION OF RETAIL OUTLET CATEGORIES

The retail outlets categories included in the survey were those that sell directly to the final consumer. Supermarkets, small shops, specialty delis, and street markets were integrated in the survey.

For the selection of the retail outlet categories, the rules were the following:

If the biggest category of retail outlets (for example supermarkets) supplied at least 80 % of the market of a RTE food category, the samples were only taken from those outlets. Where that was not the case, the second largest outlet category was added until at least 80 % of the market was covered.

2.1.3 SELECTION OF RTE FOOD CATEGORIES

Three categories of RTE food: fish food category, meat products food category and cheese food category, previously shown to be at risk of Lm contamination were sampled. The following food types were sampled in each food category:

- Fish category: packaged hot or cold smoked or gravad fish.
- Meat products category: packaged heat-treated meat products.
- Cheese category: soft or semi-soft cheese.

The number of samples taken for each category of RTE food from each retail outlet type was proportionate to the market share of that outlet type within the targeted outlet types.

2.1.4 TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENT

Temperatures were measured at the surface of the packaged samples when the samples were collected in the retail outlets.

3 RESULTS

3.1 ANALYSIS OF RTE FOOD STORAGE TEMPERATURE DATASET AT RETAIL LEVEL

3.1.1 TEMPERATURES BY RTE FOOD CATEGORIES

3.1.1.1 GENERAL ASPECTS

In total, 10 035 RTE food temperatures at retail level were recorded from 3 632 retail outlets in all participating countries.

For the three categories of RTE food considered, the distribution of temperatures registered in all participating countries is given in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures recorded on the surveyed food

RTE food categories	N	%
Fish category	3 053	30.42
Meat category	3 530	35.18
Cheese category	3 452	34.40
Total	10 035	

Figure 1: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures recorded on the surveyed foods

The proportions of RTE food temperatures recorded were balanced for each RTE food category, as designed in the sampling plan. The large dataset of storage temperatures recorded (N=10 035) give a good picture of the storage temperature of the selected RTE food all over Europe.

3.1.1.2 SURFACE STORAGE TEMPERATURE FOR CHEESE CATEGORY

Overall, 3 452 surface temperatures were recorded on soft or semi soft cheeses. The distribution of these storage temperatures is described in Table 2 through statistical parameters: mean, standard deviation, median, minimum and maximum values, the first and third quartiles.

Table 2 : Surface storage temperatures of soft or semi-soft cheeses (in °C)

Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Min	Max	First quartile	Third quartile
4.09	1.83	4.0	0	16	3.0	5.0

Figure 2: Distribution of the storage temperatures for cheese RTE food category

Figure 2 illustrates the variability of cheese temperatures recorded at retail level in all MS. The mean was 4.09 and 95% of the temperatures lies within the range [1°C - 8°C].

Figure 3: Cumulative distribution of the storage temperatures for cheese RTE food category

The graphical representation in Figure 3 gives the distribution percentiles of cheese temperatures. For example, the 75th percentile (or third quartile c.f. Table 2) was 5°C, meaning that 75% of the cheese temperatures were below this temperature.

3.1.1.3 SURFACE STORAGE TEMPERATURE FOR FISH CATEGORY

The 3 053 surface temperatures recorded on smoked or gravad fishes packaging were characterized by the statistical parameters presented in Table 3 and Figure 4.

Table 3 : Surface storage temperatures of smoked or gravad fishes (in °C)

Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Min	Max	First quartile	Third quartile
3.45	1.79	3.0	0	25	2.0	4.0

Figure 4: Distribution of the storage temperatures for fish RTE food category

According to the distribution of the fish temperatures recorded at retail level, it appears that fish temperatures are within the range [0°C - 7°C] with a 95% chance.

Figure 5: Cumulative distribution function of the storage temperatures for fish RTE food category

In Figure 5, the 75th percentile of the fish temperatures was 4°C, meaning that 75% of the population was below this temperature.

3.1.1.4 SURFACE STORAGE TEMPERATURE FOR MEAT CATEGORY

The distribution of the 3 530 storage temperatures collected for the heat-treated meat products is presented in Figure 6 and the statistical values are given in Table 4.

Table 4 : Surface storage temperature of heat-treated meat products (in °C)

Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Min	Max	First quartile	Third quartile
3.71	1.78	4.0	0	25	2.7	5.0

Figure 6: Distribution of the storage temperatures for meat RTE food category

The above distribution is characterized by an average temperature at 3.71 and meat temperatures recorded at retail level are within the range [1°C - 7°C] with 95% chance.

Figure 7: Cumulative distribution function of the storage temperatures for meat RTE food category

In Figure 7, the 75th percentile of this cumulative distribution is 5°C, this means that 75% of the fish temperatures were below 5°C.

3.1.2 TEMPERATURES BY RETAIL OUTLET CATEGORIES

3.1.2.1 GENERAL ASPECTS

In total, 3 632 retail outlets were investigated in the participating countries. In these retail outlets, 10 035 surface temperatures of packaged RTE food were recorded. These temperatures were distributed per retail outlet category, as given in Table 5 and Figure 8.

Table 5: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures recorded in each category of retail outlet

Retail outlet category	N	%
Supermarkets & small shops	9837	98.03
Street markets	24	0.24
Specialty delis	28	0.28
Others	146	1.45
Total	10 035	

Figure 8: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures per retail outlet category

The vast majority of temperatures were recorded in supermarkets and small shops, as planned in the sampling plan. By itself, this category represented 98.03% of all recorded temperatures. The two other categories, well identified, “street markets” and “specialty delis” were clearly under-represented with respectively only 0.24% and 0.28% of the recorded temperatures. The category “others” (1.45% of the recorded temperatures) was a melting pot of different sources of selling points and therefore not usable to characterize a particular type of retail.

Table 6: Surface storage temperature of RTE food by retail outlet category (in °C)

	Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Min	Max	First quartile	Third quartile
Supermarkets & small shops	3.75	1.80	4	0	25	3	5
Street markets	5.41	1.89	5	2	8	4	7
Specialty delis	4.07	1.67	4	1	8	3	5
Others	4.49	2.69	4	0	25	3	5

Supermarkets & small shops

Street markets

Specialty delis

Others

Figure 9: Distribution of RTE food storage temperatures in each retail outlet category

Table 6 and Figure 9 illustrate the variability of RTE food storage temperatures in each retail outlet category. Figure 9 gives the range where 95% of the recorded temperatures were spread.

In supermarkets and small shops, the mean temperature for the three RTE food categories surveyed was 3.75°C and 95% of the temperatures were spread between 1 and 8°C.

The mean temperatures in street markets and in specialty delis for the three RTE foods categories were respectively of 5.41°C and 4.07°C, but it is important to note that the number of data in these two categories were very low (N= 24 and 28 respectively) in comparison with supermarkets and small shops. Therefore, these data may not reflect the real storage conditions in Europe for street markets and specialty delis.

For the category “others” which gathered various types of retail outlets, the mean value (4.49°C) was similar to averages observed in the former categories, but with a higher standard deviation ($\sigma = 2.69$), probably due to the diversity of selling points investigated.

3.1.2.2 FOR CHEESE CATEGORY

Here again the number of collected temperatures in the cheese category were highly represented by supermarkets and small shops category, as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Surface storage temperature of cheese products in each retail outlet category (in °C)

	N	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Median	Min	Max	1st quartile	3rd quartile
Supermarkets & small shops	3367	4.06	1.82	4	0	16	3	5
Street markets	16	5.94	1.98	6	3	8	3	8
Specialty delis	14	4.50	1.87	5	1	7	3	6
Others	55	5.11	1.80	5	1	9	4	6

Supermarkets & small shops

Street markets

Specialty delis

Others

Figure 10 : Distribution of cheese storage temperatures by retail outlet category

As shown in Figure 10, the highest mean temperature recorded on soft or semi soft cheeses was found in street markets with a mean value equal to 5.94°C. But here again this retail outlet category was under-represented in this survey, and the confidence that can be given to this value is limited. It was the same findings for specialty delis and the category “others”.

In supermarkets and small shops the mean temperature was 4.06 and cheese temperatures were in the range [1 - 8°C], with a 95 % chance (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Cumulative distribution for cheese storage temperatures in supermarkets and small shops

In Figure 11, considering a 4°C division of the recorded temperatures, it appears that there was 63 % chance that cheese temperatures were in the range [0 -4°C], 35% chance to be in the range [4- 8°C] 1.4 % chance to be in the range [8 - 12°C] Due to a marked flattening of curve from 8°C till the end of the curve, there was only 0.1 % chance to be equal or above 12°C.

3.1.2.3 FOR FISH CATEGORY

Most of the fish temperature products recorded came from supermarkets and small shops, distributed as shown in Table 8..

Table 8: Surface storage temperature of fish products per retail outlet category (in °C)

	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Supermarkets and small shops	3005	3.44	1.73	0	23
Street markets	2	4.50	0.71	4	5
Specialty delis	4	4.00	2.83	2	8
Others	43	4.58	4.10	0	25

Figure 12: Distributions of fish storage temperatures in supermarkets and small shops

According to Figure 12, the mean temperature for the fish category was 3.44°C in supermarkets and small shops and fish temperatures were in the range of [0 -7°C] with 95% chance.

Here again, regarding a 4°C division of the recorded fish temperatures, it appears that there was 79% chance that these temperatures were below or equal to 4°C, 21 % chance that temperatures were within the range [4 – 8°C], 0.5 % chance that temperatures lies in the range [8 - 12°C] and only 0.2% chance to be equal or over 12°C.

The results of the three others categories (street markets, specialty delis and “others” are not illustrated due to insufficient data.

3.1.2.4 FOR MEAT CATEGORY

98% of the meat temperatures recorded came from supermarkets and small shops, and were distributed as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Surface storage temperature of meat products for each retail outlet category (in °C)

	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Supermarkets and small shops	3466	3.73	1.76	0	25
Street markets	6	4.33	1.37	2	6
Specialty delis	11	3.55	0.52	3	4
Others	47	3.60	4.10	0	6

Figure 13: Distributions of meat storage temperatures in supermarkets and small shops

As shown in Figure 13, the majority (95%) of meat products were sold between 1 and 7°C, but like for cheese and fish temperatures it seems interesting to look at the proportion of meat temperatures spread in these regular intervals of 4°C, some of them representing abusive storage conditions. The right curve (cumulative distribution) shows that there was 72 % chance that meat temperatures were in the range [0 – 4°C], 27 % chance to be within the range [4 - 8°C], 0.9 % within the range [8 -12°C] and only 0.1% chance to be equal or over 12°C.

3.1.3 TEMPERATURES BY SEASON

In order to detect a possible seasonal effect of the external temperature on the storage temperature of RTE food at retail level, an analysis by season was carried out.

The timing of sampling has been set up over the year in order to take into account a possible variation in the contamination level of *Listeria monocytogenes* in RTE food. Thus, the surface temperatures of the packaged samples were also recorded during a 12-month period, with an equal number of data collected per month (see Table 10 and Figure 14).

Table 10: Distribution of RTE food storage temperatures recorded per season

Season	N	%
Autumn	2998	29.88
Winter	2113	21.06
Spring	2278	22.70
Summer	2646	26.37
Total	10 035	

The same proportion of RTE food storage temperatures were collected at each season.

Figure 14: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures per season

Table 11 : Surface storage temperature of RTE food by season (in °C)

	Mean	Stand. Dev.	Median	Min	Max	1st quartile	3rd quartile
Autumn	3.78	1.67	4.0	0	12	3.0	5.0
Winter	3.62	1.82	3.90	0	25	2.0	5.0
Spring	3.82	1.93	4.0	0	25	2.0	5.0
Summer	3.82	1.85	4.0	0	16	2.8	7.0

Figure 15: Distribution of RTE food storage temperatures by season

Whatever the season, the mean surface temperatures of RTE food categories at retail level were around 3.8 °C (see Table 11) and these storage temperatures were within the range [0 - 8°C] (see figure 15 with 95% chance).

Figure 16: Mean storage temperatures of each RTE food category per season

The lowest average temperature was observed for RTE fish category, and the highest average temperature for RTE cheese products, whatever the season (see Figure 16).

3.1.4 TEMPERATURES BY GEOCLIMATIC DIVISION

The 26 EU MSs and one non-MS (Norway) were clustered according the Köppen-Geiger climate classification (classification based on temperature and rainfall), into four areas (see Figure 17):

- Eastern Europe: Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia.
- Western Europe: Belgium, France, Germany, Ireland, Luxembourg, Netherlands, United Kingdom.
- Northern Europe: Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway, Sweden.
- Southern Europe: Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain.

Figure 17: Map of the European countries participating to the survey and clustered according the climate classification of Köppen Geiger

Table 12: Distribution of RTE food storage temperatures recorded per geoclimatic division

Geoclimatic division	N	%
Eastern Europe	1741	17.35
Western Europe	5016	49.99
Northern Europe	1018	10.14
Southern Europe	2260	22.52
Total	10 035	

Figure 16: Breakdown of RTE food storage temperatures per geoclimatic division

According to Table 12 and Figure 16, half of the collected temperature came from Western Europe due to the fact that in the sampling plan, samples were allocated to every Member State proportionally to the size of the human population in each Member State.

Table 13: Surface storage temperature of RTE food by geoclimatic division (in °C)

	Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Min	Max	1st quartile	3rd quartile
Eastern Europe	3.45	1.60	3.0	0	23	2.0	4.0
Western Europe	3.88	1.93	4.0	0	25	3.0	5.0
Northern Europe	4.37	1.89	4.0	0	15	3.0	5.0
Southern Europe	3.50	1.56	3.2	0	13	2.6	4.0

Figure 19: Distribution of RTE food storage temperatures per geoclimatic area

Figure 19 shows that, 95% of RTE foods were sold between a low temperature equal to 0°C or 1°C and a high temperature equal to 7°C or 8°C, whatever the geoclimatic division where these products were sold.

Figure 20: Mean storage temperatures of each RTE food category per geoclimatic division

According to Figure 20, it seems that cheese and meat products were stored at a little higher temperature in Northern Europe than in the other areas, but all these temperatures were within a short range and the maximum average value observed was below 5°C.

4 CONCLUSION

The baseline survey has been conducted to assess the prevalence and the level of contamination of *Listeria monocytogenes* in three categories of RTE food. It also provided interesting data on the distribution of RTE food temperatures at retail level in Europe.

The statistical analyses of the temperatures recorded at the surface of the packaging of the considered products show that in supermarkets and small shops (the largest retail outlet category represented in this survey), RTE food products were sold at an average temperature of 4°C all over Europe.

Thus one can be confident that RTE food sold in supermarkets and small shops are maintained at low refrigerated temperatures. The storage conditions in this outlet category seem appropriate to preserve the food quality and the food safety. However, we may regret that small shops were not considered separately from supermarkets.

This study shows also that the RTE products investigated were sold at an average temperature of 4.06°C for cheese products, of 3.45°C for fish products and for 3.71°C for meat products. This study also points out that these products are sold between 0°C and 8°C with 95% chance, and in the worst case, have only 0.2% chance to be sold over or at the abuse temperature of 12°C.

The knowledge on storage temperatures of RTE food at retail acquired in this study could be used by DG SANTE together with Member States to improve the implementation of durability studies and challenge testing, by better simulating the cold chain and submit products to the foreseeable conditions of RTE distribution, as recommended in EC Regulation 2073/2005.

More precisely, the outcome of this study could be taken into consideration to redefine the temperature profile at retail level to conduct challenge tests, as defined in Table 3 of the "EURL *Lm* technical guidance document for conducting RTE shelf-life studies relating to *Listeria monocytogenes*" (2014).

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